

Journal of Health and Medical Sciences

Supriani, N. N. D., Sirat, N. M., Senjaya, A. A., Ratmini, N. K., Ariana, I. K., & Yulianti, A. E. (2024), Preference of the Mouthwash Ingredients Wild Cosmos Leaf Extract (*Cosmos Caudatus*) among Organoleptic Test Panelists. *Journal of Health and Medical Sciences*, 7(4), 72-78.

ISSN 2622-7258

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1994.07.04.330

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Health and Medical Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Journal of Health and Medical Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Medicine and Public Health, including medicine, surgery, ophthalmology, gynecology and obstetrics, psychiatry, anesthesia, pediatrics, orthopedics, microbiology, pathology and laboratory medicine, medical education, research methodology, forensic medicine, medical ethics, community medicine, public health, community health, behavioral health, health policy, health service, health education, health economics, medical ethics, health protection, environmental health, and equity in health. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Health and Medical Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Health and Medical Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Preference of the Mouthwash Ingredients Wild Cosmos Leaf Extract (*Cosmos Caudatus*) among Organoleptic Test Panelists

Ni Nyoman Dewi Supariani¹, Ni Made Sirat², Asep Arifin Senjaya³, Ni Ketut Ratmini⁴, I Ketut Ariana⁵,
Anisyah Elly Yulianti⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Department of Dental Health, Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar, Indonesia

Correspondence: Ni Nyoman Dewi Supariani, Department of Dental Health, Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar, 80224, Indonesia. E-mail: dewisupariani66@gmail.com

Abstract

Kenikir leaves are one of the traditional medicines used in Indonesia, yet only some studies investigate the compounds tested against them. This study aimed to evaluate Kenikir leaves as mouthwash with organoleptic tests and determine the differences in preferences. This type of research is quasi-experimental. The sample size is 32 people as organoleptic test panelists. The parameters were the color, smell, and taste of Kenikir leaf extract mouthwash material with original, mint, and mixed fruit flavors with a hedonic scale with ethnic groups of Jawa, Flores, Lombok, Bali, and Timor. The study results showed that regarding the color, the panelists preferred the mixed fruit color, with a $p = 0.032$ ($p < 0.05$). Regarding the smell, the panelists preferred the mixed fruit with $p = 0.019$ ($p < 0.05$). The panelists preferred the taste of mouthwash ingredients with mint flavor, but the assessment difference was insignificant at $p = 0.276$ ($p > 0.05$). Timor people like the product most. Meanwhile, the Flores ethnic group hardly likes all mouthwash products with Kenikir leaf extract. In conclusion, most preferred organoleptic test panelists of mouthwash ingredients are mouthwash ingredients with mixed fruit aroma/smell, color, and mint flavor.

Keywords: Organoleptic Test, Panelist, Mouthwash, Kenikir (*Cosmos Caudatus*)

1. Introduction

Plaque contains many bacteria, and inflammation can occur in the gingival tissue (Murakami et al., 2018). Gingivitis is caused by deposits of microbial plaque, usually in or near the gingival sulcus. Maintaining oral hygiene is of utmost importance to stop the progression of the disease. Plaque control is one of the most integral methods to control bacterial growth. Mechanical plaque control is the primary method for removing and controlling plaque, and toothbrushing plays a significant role. (Balan et al., 2018; Preethi & Ramamurthy, 2015).

About 80% of people around the globe rely on traditional medicine. As many as 170 of the 194 WHO Member States have reported using conventional medicine. Most Indonesians, especially in rural areas, also use traditional herbal medicines. Kenikir, known as the wild cosmos or *Cosmos caudatus*, is one of the vegetables Indonesians often consume. This is because the kenikir is an herbal plant that benefits human health. Research shows that Kenikir leaves extracted using ethanol and other solvents showed the presence of active compounds flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids, tannins, and polyphenols (Utami et al., 2024). Research also shows that kenikir leaves contain alkaloids, triterpenoids, phenolics, quinones, and flavonoids by phytochemical screening by methanol extract. Meanwhile, the ethanol extract contains flavonoids, saponins, phenolics, alkaloids, and quinones (Masitah et al., 2023; Phong et al., 2022).

Organoleptic testing is an evaluation that relies on the sensory perception process. This sensing process is described as a physio-psychological activity involving the awareness or recognition of an object's characteristics due to sensory stimulation from the object. Measurement of assessment using the five human senses is also called sensory assessment and is subjective. Organoleptic assessment requires a panel of people or groups to assess the quality of the product. The assessment usually takes the subjectivity of impressions (Damaziak et al., 2019; Sipos et al., 2021). People who are panel members are called panelists. Although traditional medicine has been used for a long time, it is not completely safe because it is a strange compound to the body, so it is very important to know its potential toxicity. Toxic effects on living things can be seen and may not be if the dose absorbed is relatively tiny. The damage can be limited to cells only (Aydm et al., 2016; Mihafu et al., 2020; Quintanilla-Casas et al., 2020).

This research aims to investigate the preference of panelists for the organoleptic test towards kenikir extract as a mouthwash.

2. Method

This quasi-experimental study of organoleptic testing was conducted with a post-test-only design without a control group design. The population of panelists are several Indonesian ethnic groups, namely Javanese, Flores, Lombok, Balinese, and Timorese, who lived in Denpasar City and its surroundings and came to fulfill the invitation to get an explanation before being selected as untrained panelists. The sample size in this study was 32 people, with an equal number of men and women. Samples of mouthwash extract from kenikir leaves were provided to panelists randomly, and the panelists' booth was also provided randomly.

The inclusion criteria include male or female adults aged between 20-35 years, 1) Male or female adults aged between 20-35 years, able to read and write, serious, open, and honest, healthy, and not suffering from illnesses that can influence the vision, smell, and taste. Meanwhile, the sample exclusion criteria are those who do not heed the prohibitions required during the study, are absent during the survey, resigning after completing the informed consent.

The data collection was for the color, smell, and taste of the kenikir leaf extract mouthwash using a hedonic scale with five measurement digits, namely: Strongly like (5), Like (4), Neutral/Neither Agree nor Disagree (3), Dislike (2) Strongly Dislike (1). Each panelist was given an assessment sheet in the form of a checklist.

The research was performed first by preparing kenikir leaf extract and producing it as a mouthwash. Later, the researchers looked for volunteers who were willing to be untrained panelists. Once the volunteers or the samples were obtained, an informed consent was signed. An interview was also performed with volunteers with questions and answers to determine their background and health conditions. The panelist selection stage was carried out based on intuition and rationality toward the sensitivity and knowledge of prospective panelists. Besides, the preparation of the tasting room and its completeness were also accomplished.

The collected assessment data were analyzed univariately, namely descriptive tests to determine the frequency and percentage, and then the differences in data between groups were tested using the Kruskal Wallis test.

3. Results

The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test of the panelists' organoleptic assessment of the color, smell, and taste of the mouthwash material made from kenikir leaf extract with various flavors are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mouthwash evaluation from the color, smell, and taste

No.	Mouthwash evaluation parameter	Flavor	n	Mean Rank	X ²	df	p-value
1.	Color	Original	32	42.84	6.883	2	0.032
		Mint		44.28			
		Mixed fruit		58.36			
2.	Smell	Original	32	39.17	7.931	2	0.019
		Mint		48.89			
		Mixed fruit		57.44			
3.	Taste	Original	32	45.06	2.573	2	0.276
		Mint		54.70			
		Mixed fruit		45.73			

Table 1 shows that the panelists most liked mixed fruit colors. The result of p-value is 0.032 ($p < 0.05$). The smell parameter got the same result that mixed fruit color dominates with a p-value of 0.019 ($p < 0.05$). Meanwhile, for the taste, the panelists prefer the mint flavor to mixed fruit and original flavors, with a p-value of 0.276 ($p > 0.05$).

Table 2: Assessment based on color with the Kruskal-Wallis test

Parameter	Flavor	Ethnic Group	n	Mean Rank	X ²	df	p-value
Color	<i>Original</i>	Jawa	6	12.83	9.736	4	0.045
		Flores	6	15.50			
		Lombok	6	9.42			
		Bali	6	22.50			
		Timor	8	21.81			
	<i>Mint</i>	Jawa	6	15.92	4.048	4	0.400
		Flores	6	15.25			
		Lombok	6	11.33			
		Bali	6	21.00			
		Timor	8	18.38			
	<i>Mixed Fruit</i>	Jawa	6	18.08	5.696	4	0.223
		Flores	6	10.08			
		Lombok	6	16.00			
		Bali	6	16.08			
		Timor	8	20.81			

Table 2 shows that the Balinese liked the original flavor color the most, with a p-value of 0.045. Meanwhile, for mint, the Balinese also liked it the most, with a p-value of 0.400. However, in the mixed fruit, Timorese liked the most compared to other ethnic groups, with a p-value of 0.223.

Table 3: Assessment based on smell with the Kruskal-Wallis test

Parameter	Flavor	Ethnic Group	n	Mean Rank	X ²	df	p-value
Smell	<i>Original</i>	Jawa	6	14.83	4.448	4	0.349
		Flores	6	12.33			
		Lombok	6	14.67			
		Bali	6	17.17			
		Timor	8	21.75			
	<i>Mint</i>	Jawa	6	21.00	3.195	4	0.526
		Flores	6	12.50			
		Lombok	6	15.92			
		Bali	6	15.00			
		Timor	8	17.69			
		Jawa	6	20.17			

<i>Mixed</i>	Flores	6	11.33	6.668	4	0.155
<i>Fruit</i>	Lombok	6	18.92			
	Bali	6	12.25			
	Timor	8	19.00			

Table 5 shows no significant difference in preference because the p-value is more than 0.05 i.e. 0.349, 0.526, and 0.155.

Table 4: Assessment based on taste with the Kruskal-Wallis test

Parameter	Flavor	Ethnic Group	n	Mean Rank	X ²	df	p-value
Taste	Original	Jawa	6	16.33	4.776	4	0.311
		Flores	6	13.67			
		Lombok	6	15.17			
		Bali	6	13.67			
		Timor	8	21.88			
	Mint	Jawa	6	18.00	2.376	4	0.667
		Flores	6	12.33			
		Lombok	6	15.00			
		Bali	6	17.00			
	Mixed Fruit	Jawa	6	16.83	10.850	4	0.028
		Flores	6	10.00			
		Lombok	6	14.33			
Bali		6	13.67				
		Timor	8	24.88			

Table 4 shows no significant difference in preference between ethnic groups regarding the taste of flavored mouthwash ingredients with p-values of 0.311, 0.667, and 0.028 respectively for original, mint, and mixed fruit flavors.

Table 5: Preference of panelists in organoleptic tests of mouthwash products with various flavors

No.	Experiment	n	Mean Rank	X ²	df	p-value
1.	Color in original flavor		290.80			
2.	Color in mint flavor		296.17			
3.	Color in mixed fruit flavor		366.34			
4.	Smell in original flavor		318.28			
5.	Smell in mint flavor	32	383.09	98.951	17	0.000
6.	Smell in mixed fruit flavor		432.02			
7.	Taste in original flavor		275.09			
8.	Taste in mint flavor		334.38			
9.	Taste in mixed fruit flavor		282.11			

Table 5 shows that the most preferred mouthwash product for its smell and color is a mixed fruit and mint flavors. Meanwhile, for the taste, the panelists prefer mint and mixed fruit flavors. The difference in this assessment is significant at $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$).

4. Discussion

Researchers have widely used the hedonic test to measure the product level. Six levels are used in hedonic measurement, i.e., strongly like, like, somewhat like, neutral, dislike, and strongly dislike. This test is also widely used to evaluate final products. A hedonic scale can be used to determine differences in practice. Hedonic tests require a certain number of panelists (Gusti Agung Ayu Hari Triandini & Gde Adi Suryawan Wangiyana, 2023; Zuhdi & Khairi, 2022).

The results of the descriptive test in this study showed that for the mouthwash material of kenikir leaf extract, most panelists, namely 34.4% and 53.1%, stated that they strongly liked the color of the mouthwash material, while

40.6% stated that they neutral about the color of the mouthwash material. The results show that regarding the color, the panelists prefer the mixed fruit to mint and original flavors. The difference in the evaluation indicates significance with a $p = 0.032$ ($p < 0.05$). This shows that the organoleptic test panelists preferred the color of the mouthwash material with mixed fruit flavor over other flavors.

The evaluation of the smell parameter shows that most panelists (34.38%, 46.88%, and 62.5%) said they strongly like mouthwash with original, mint, and mixed fruit flavors. Only a tiny portion, namely 3.13%, 3.13%, and 0% stated they strongly dislike the smell of the kenikir leaf extract mouthwash. The panelists' assessment of the smell of the mouthwash showed that they prefer the smell of the mouthwash with mixed fruit flavor. The difference result is significant at $p = 0.019$ ($p < 0.05$). These results indicate that the panelists preferred the smell of the mouthwash with mixed fruit flavor to the others, and this difference in preference was significant at $p < 0.05$.

A neutral evaluation was obtained when the panelists assessed the taste of the mouthwash, in detail 56.25% of respondents. However, for the mouthwash with mint and mixed fruit flavors, the majority of panelists, namely 34.38% and 31.25%, said they strongly liked the taste. The analysis shows that the organoleptic test panelists preferred the taste of the mouthwash with mint flavor, mixed fruit, and original flavors, respectively. However, the assessment difference is insignificant at $p = 0.276$ ($p > 0.05$). These results indicate that panelists prefer the mouthwash's taste with mint flavor to the others.

The results of the organoleptic assessment based on the ethnic groups' preference for the color of the original mouthwash show that the Balinese prefer the color of the original mouthwash, followed by the Timor, Flores, Java, and Lombok groups. This difference in preference is significant with a $p = 0.045$ ($p < 0.05$). In the assessment of preference for mouthwash with mint and mixed fruit flavors between the ethnic groups, there is no significant difference with a value of $p = 0.400$ and $p = 0.223$ ($p > 0.05$).

The result data on the parameter of smell present no significant difference in preference. The same results were also obtained in the preference for ethnic groups. The Kruskal-Wallis test expresses that the most preferred mouthwash product is a mouthwash with mixed fruit and mint based on smell and color.

The findings of this study indicate that the mouthwash formula made from kenikir leaf extract could serve as a herbal product in the country, aligning with the "back to nature" approach. This method allows for the incorporation of various herbal ingredients as antimicrobial agents in different cosmetic products, including mouthwash. Given that the use of herbal medicines in the world continues to increase, as well as in Indonesia, it is expected that drug manufacturers will be interested in continuing to develop herbal medicines, especially kenikir leaf extract (Ahmed et al., 2023; Chaachouay & Zidane, 2024; Rahayu et al., 2020). The results of this study describe organoleptic test panelists' preference for mouthwash products with kenikir leaf extract. The most preferred mouthwash formula is a formula with mint and mixed fruit flavors so that it can be used as a reference if this formula is to be developed into a product with economic value.

It is recommended for future research to conduct similar research with an interview with panelist regarding their habits of using other brands of mouthwash with similar flavors, such as mint and mixed fruit. This will affect the panelists' assessment of the mouthwash and toothpaste products with kenikir leaf extract because the subjective and psychological reactions of the panelists also influence the organoleptic evaluation. Several of these panelists stated that the mouthwash product, especially with the original flavor, felt sticky on the tongue and tasted bitter, so people rarely prefer it.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, NNDS and NMS.; Methodology, NNDS; Software, AAS, NKR; Validation, NNDS, IKA; Formal Analysis, AEY; Investigation, AEY; Resources, IKA; Data Curation, NNDS, NMS; Writing – Original Draft Preparation, IKA and AEY; Writing – Review & Editing, AAS; Visualization, NMS and AAS; Supervision, NNDS; Project Administration, NNDS; Funding Acquisition, NNDS.

Funding: This research was funded by the Ministry of Health Indonesia with grant number HK.03.02/F.XXXII/3043/2024.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics approval: All subjects gave their informed consent for inclusion before they participated in the study. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and the protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar Number DP.04.02/F.XXXII.25/0764/2024.

Acknowledgements: The authors would like to thank the Ministry of Health of Indonesia and Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar for their support during the research.

References

- Ahmed, A., Shuaib, M., Shirsat, M. K., & Sharma, D. (2023). Herbal Medicines and Recent Development on Novel Herbal Drug Delivery System. *Indonesian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, 6(1), 13–24. <https://doi.org/10.32734/idjpcr.v6i1.11702>
- Aydn, A., Aktay, G., & Yesilada, E. (2016). A Guidance Manual for the Toxicity Assessment of Traditional Herbal Medicines. *Natural Product Communications*, 11(11), 1763–1773.
- Balan, P., Chong, Y. S., Umashankar, S., Swarup, S., Loke, W. M., Lopez, V., He, H. G., & Seneviratne, C. J. (2018). Keystone Species in Pregnancy Gingivitis: A Snapshot of Oral Microbiome During Pregnancy and Postpartum Period. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 9, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.02360>
- Chaachouay, N., & Zidane, L. (2024). Plant-Derived Natural Products: A Source for Drug Discovery and Development. *Drugs and Drug Candidates*, 3(1), 184–207. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ddc3010011>
- Damaziak, K., Stelmasiak, A., Riedel, J., Zdanowska-Sąsiadek, Ż., Buclaw, M., Gozdowski, D., & Michalczyk, M. (2019). Sensory evaluation of poultry meat: A comparative survey of results from normal sighted and blind people. *PLOS ONE*, 14(1), e0210722. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0210722>
- Gusti Agung Ayu Hari Triandini, I., & Gde Adi Suryawan Wangiyana, I. (2023). Hedonic test of Lombok Island palm sugar candy formulated with Multi-Purpose Tree Species (MPTS) leaves infusion. *Journal of Agritech and Food Processing*, 3(2), 1–9.
- Masitah, Pribadi, T., Pratama, I. M., Harist, R. F., Sari, P. A., Dianita, F., & Setiawan, V. K. (2023). Analisis Kandungan Metabolik Sekunder pada Daun Kenikir (*Cosmos Caudatus* Kunth.) dengan Pelarut Metanol, Etanol, dan Etil Asetat (Analysis of Secondary Metabolic Content in Kenikir Leaves (*Cosmos Caudatus* Kunth.) with Methanol, Ethanol, and Ethyl Acetate Solvents). *Biedukasi Jurnal Pendidikan Biologi*, 14(2), 266–272.
- Mihafu, F. D., Issa, J. Y., & Kamiyango, M. W. (2020). Implication of Sensory Evaluation and Quality Assessment in Food Product Development: A Review. *Current Research in Nutrition and Food Science Journal*, 8(3), 690–702. <https://doi.org/10.12944/CRNFSJ.8.3.03>
- Murakami, S., Mealey, B. L., Mariotti, A., & Chapple, I. L. C. (2018). Dental plaque-induced gingival conditions. *Journal of Periodontology*, 89(S1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/JPER.17-0095>
- Phong, H. X., Viet, N. T., Quyen, N. T. N., Van Thinh, P., Trung, N. M., & Ngan, T. T. K. (2022). Phytochemical screening, total phenolic, flavonoid contents, and antioxidant activities of four spices commonly used in Vietnamese traditional medicine. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 56, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.12.142>
- Preethi, R., & Ramamurthy, J. (2015). Pregnancy Gingivitis. *Article in Research Journal of Pharmaceutical Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 6(1), 1–5. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281992871>
- Quintanilla-Casas, B., Marin, M., Guardiola, F., García-González, D. L., Barbieri, S., Bendini, A., Gallina Toschi, T., Vichi, S., & Tres, A. (2020). Supporting the Sensory Panel to Grade Virgin Olive Oils: An In-House-Validated Screening Tool by Volatile Fingerprinting and Chemometrics. *Foods*, 9(10), 1509. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9101509>
- Rahayu, Y. Y. S., Araki, T., & Rosleine, D. (2020). Factors affecting the use of herbal medicines in the universal health coverage system in Indonesia. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 260, 112974. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2020.112974>
- Sipos, L., Nyitrai, Á., Hitka, G., Friedrich, L. F., & Kókai, Z. (2021). Sensory Panel Performance Evaluation—Comprehensive Review of Practical Approaches. *Applied Sciences*, 11(24), 11977. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112411977>

- Utami, Y. P., Imrawati, I., Ismail, I., Mus, S., Jariah, A., Mustarin, R., Lestari, W. O. D. A. M., & Waliulu, S. (2024). Optimisation of Phenolic Content and Antibacterial Activity of *Cosmos caudatus* Kunth. Leaf Ethanol Extract Using different Drying Techniques. *Tropical Journal of Natural Product Research*, 8(1), 5825–5831. <https://doi.org/10.26538/tjnpr/v8i1.17>
- Zuhdi, M., & Khairi, A. N. (2022). Analysis of organoleptic properties and consumer acceptance of frozen noodle products. *Journal of Halal Science and Research*, 3(1), 15–19. <https://doi.org/10.12928/jhsr.v3i1.6828>